

Emulator-based calibration of a dynamic grassland model using recurrent neural networks and Hamiltonian Monte Carlo

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ABSTRACT

Process-based models are versatile tools for understanding and monitoring the carbon cycle in agricultural ecosystems. Their large-scale application is often hindered by computational challenges, particularly in iterative processes such as calibration. Machine learning emulation offers a practical solution by substituting the process-based model with a computationally less expensive approximation.

In this study, we build a neural network emulator for a dynamic agroecosystem model. The procedure included obtaining training data from model simulations, defining hyperparameter space for the neural network model, hyperparameter optimization and training the network and evaluation with 5-fold cross validation. We apply the method for BASGRA, a process-based model for managed grasslands, to predict weekly values of leaf area index (LAI) gross and net primary productivity (GPP and NPP), soil moisture and harvest yield over a year, with weekly meteorological data and soil properties, and a subset of model parameters as input. The emulator explained over 95% of the variation of the process-based model for each output variable, showing high predictive accuracy. We then apply the emulator for calibrating model parameters against GPP data from three Finnish sites and perform 71 calibration experiments with different calibration and validation data sets. The predictive performance of GPP is improved across all experiments, with 33%–64% reduction in RMSE, while also informing LAI and harvest carbon estimation. This study shows one of the first successful applications of emulating temporal dynamics of agroecosystem models to facilitate large-scale calibration.

1. Introduction

Reliable monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) of carbon emission and sequestration in agroecosystems is essential for better managing the fields and contributing to climate change mitigation (Smith et al., 2020). However, quantifying carbon dynamics in agroecosystems is challenging because making direct measurements on all relevant processes, stocks and fluxes at scale is both costly and susceptible to large uncertainties. When combined with measurements, process-based models of agroecosystems that simulate carbon dynamics by incorporating environmental conditions and management practices can greatly help predicting carbon exchange (Smith et al., 2012). However, the intricate structure of process-based models make them computationally intensive and inefficient for producing large numbers of simulations, required in sensitivity analysis, model calibration or other tasks that involve confronting models with big data (Fer et al., 2018; Stanfill et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2019). Emulation of process-based models enables enhanced scalability to large data sets and exploration of different scenarios more efficiently. Emulators are increasingly used in different fields to facilitate large scale simulations

and once trained they can achieve simulations of orders of magnitudes faster than the process-based model (Reichstein et al., 2019). Generally, emulators are computationally efficient models approximating process-based models and can serve as their substitutes, facilitating iterative sampling of parameters and numerous simulations under the different parameter configurations (Pianosi et al., 2016).

Emulation is especially valuable for efficient model calibration. While process-based agroecosystem models are useful for synthesizing available information and extending the calculations into new sites, time periods or environmental conditions, the uncertainties associated with their predictions also need to be addressed and constrained. Uncertainties in process-based agroecosystem models stem from different sources, one of which can be model parameters describing soil and vegetation properties (Wallach et al., 2021). These properties are usually not precisely known, while some can be approximated based on available knowledge and direct measurements, some need to be estimated indirectly through methods that inversely inform parameter values by identifying values that lead to more accurate model simulations aligned with measured data. Calibration of the model by

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seeking better model-data alignment constrains parameter uncertainty and improves model accuracy, enhancing the reliability of the model. Systematic calibration of process-based models is a part of greenhouse gas certification standards such as Verra (2023).

Bayesian calibration is a recommended formal approach for parameter estimation of process-based models, as it incorporates prior knowledge with observational data and quantifies uncertainty in predictions (van Oijen, 2017; Hartig et al., 2012). The Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm is a widely used Bayesian numerical method for sampling the potentially complex a posteriori parameter distribution (van Oijen et al., 2005; Lu et al., 2017). The calibration process with MCMC algorithm can involve tens of thousands to hundreds of millions of iterations, making it computationally intensive, particularly with high-dimensional parameter spaces. This often makes traditional MCMC-based calibration methods infeasible to perform in practice due to prohibitively expensive computation time (Fer et al., 2018).

This is where emulator-based calibration comes into play to address the inefficiency in MCMC-calibration of process-based agroecosystem models. There are different machine learning (ML) emulation options available such as random forest, Gaussian processes or the multivariate regression splines, which have been successfully applied in agroecosystem emulation (Johnston et al., 2023; Xiao et al., 2022; Heimsch et al., 2024). Alternative ML emulation methods offer different trade-offs. For example, Gaussian Process (GP) emulation has been previously used in calibration of one such agroecosystem model, namely BASGRA (Heimsch et al., 2024), applying the method described in Fer et al. (2018), which emulates the likelihood instead of the model outputs. GP emulators provide advantageous properties for Bayesian calibration where i) they go through the exact training points rather than smoothing them, ii) estimate uncertainties associated with interpolation and iii) show high fidelity to the emulated model (Fer et al., 2018). However, the computational cost increases significantly with the amount of design (training) points, due to the inversion of the covariance matrices in the process (Baker et al., 2022). Consequently, the Gaussian process-approach in calibration tasks with larger spatio-temporal scales or parameter spaces would be increasingly computationally heavy. Additionally, GP emulators and other above-mentioned methods have limitations in learning temporal dependencies which makes them unsuitable for emulating process-based model time-series outputs that can have broader use cases besides calibration.

Emulation of time-series outputs enables studying temporal dynamics in the carbon exchange of the agroecosystem, which allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem processes. For example, instead of averaging the carbon dynamics related outputs to annual values, an emulator that can produce weekly values provides more insight on short term variations and seasonal trends in carbon dynamics of the ecosystem, critical for understanding the effect of management practices or weather events. An emulator capable of modeling temporal variations in carbon dynamics provides more detailed information for calibration, enhancing its utility.

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are designed for learning temporal patterns from time-series inputs and can be used to produce time-series outputs (Goodfellow et al., 2016), which other ML methods struggle to model effectively. RNNs can iteratively go through a sequential input, producing an output for each time step and learn dependencies between them. They have been applied in data-driven agroecosystem modeling (Liu et al., 2022b; Zou et al., 2024) and hybrid agroecosystem modeling (Liu et al., 2022a, 2024), and RNN-based emulators have been constructed for hydrological studies (Mohammed et al., 2022; Qi et al., 2022). Although the application of RNN emulators in agroecosystem modeling is still emerging, the mentioned applications demonstrate their potential for agroecosystem model emulation.

A widely used and efficient recurrent neural network, Long short-term memory network (LSTM) (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997), learns by selectively updating and forgetting information at each time

step in a sequence, based on corresponding input and saved information from previous time steps. The LSTM has demonstrated applicability in emulation tasks modeling time-series outputs (Mohammed et al., 2022; Qi et al., 2022; Wesselkamp et al., 2024) and capability of learning dependencies within meteorological, soil property and phenological data, as demonstrated in data-driven yield modeling (Liu et al., 2022b; Schwalbert et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2022).

While RNNs are required for learning temporal dependencies and producing time-series outputs, pairing them with the fundamental neural networks, feed-forward neural networks (FNNs), is beneficial for further processing static inputs or representations learned by RNNs and reshaping the outputs into the desired format for producing the final prediction. FNNs excel in learning static dependencies in data and have been widely used in emulation of land system models in tasks with non-sequential outputs. FNNs have been applied at larger spatial scales for modeling carbon fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems (Lu and Ricciuto, 2019; Dagon et al., 2020), where focus was spatial variation of annual values. Also Nguyen et al. (2019) focused on emulating annual values of soil organic carbon and crop yield of agricultural sites with FNNs. Nevertheless, for modeling temporal variation in agroecosystems, FNNs are limited as they process each input independently and do not learn temporal dependencies dynamically. Yet, when combined with RNNs, they can further refine the model's predictions by learning static dependencies.

In addition to their desirable technical abilities, NNs also present practical advantages. For instance, neural networks process data in batches and leverage parallel computations, enabling efficient processing of large data sets across multiple sites and years. Furthermore, machine-learning frameworks like JAX (Bradbury et al., 2018) provide autodifferentiation and GPU compatibility, enabling efficient gradient evaluation, which in turn can be exploited in gradient-based MCMC methods such as No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS, Hoffman and Gelman, 2014).

In this study we focus on emulating BASGRA, a process-based model for grassland dynamics, and aim to improve its predictive accuracy by refining the parameter values of the model. BASGRA has been previously calibrated with traditional MCMC methods (Höglind et al., 2020; Persson et al., 2024) and a GP emulator-based method (Heimsch et al., 2024). We take a new approach with neural network emulation for efficient Bayesian model calibration. Our objective is to first optimize a neural network model for time-dependent emulation of BASGRA and evaluate the performance for multiple outputs. Second, we aim to test the emulator's potential for low-cost model calibration, using a Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) algorithm, and compare the performance on single and multi-site calibration setups.

The process for building the emulator includes first creating training data with input-output pairs from process-based model simulations, with 5 separate sets in order to perform 5-fold cross validation. Secondly, the NN architecture, including order and size of the layers LSTM and FNN, is optimized by training the network multiple times with different hyperparameters from a predefined space. The best performing emulator is then used in calibration, in place of the process-based model. To the best of our knowledge, this approach is a new advancement in agroecosystem modeling, emulating the temporal dynamics of agroecosystem models to facilitate calibration of large process-based models.

2. Data and methods

2.1. BASGRA_N: A process-based model for managed grasslands

BASGRA (the Basic Grassland Model) (Höglind et al., 2016, 2020) is a dynamic process-based model for managed grasslands. BASGRA simulates daily greenhouse gas fluxes, harvest yield, digestibility of stems and leaves. The model includes processes and variables for representing above and below-ground carbon stocks and fluxes, plant phenology,

plant and soil water, and snow depth. The model inputs consist of daily meteorological drivers such as air-temperature, precipitation, radiation and humidity, and management activity such as harvest events. The model parameters include soil and plant properties, such as parameters of water retention and plant growth (Table 1, Höglind et al., 2020). The emulator was trained using the BASGRA_N model version, which is capable of simulating the effect of nitrogen (N) supply on plants and their environment. However, the emulator does not include N supply related management variables, and accordingly, N-cycle processes were inactive in the simulations included to the training set. Thus, we hereafter refer to BASGRA_N as BASGRA for simplicity.

2.2. Building the emulator

Our objective was to emulate key features in plant CO₂ exchange over cultivated boreal grasslands with neural networks. We generated the training data for the emulator from input–output pairs of BASGRA simulations. The emulator input included weekly averaged meteorological data, harvest days, soil hydraulic properties, and a subset of model parameters selected with an uncertainty analysis (Table 1). The output variables of interest to emulate included leaf area index (LAI), net primary production (NPP), gross primary production (GPP), soil moisture and the harvest carbon flux, also averaged to weekly values for computational efficiency as explained below.

2.2.1. Emulator training data

For each simulation included in the training data, we sampled a model parameter vector from the distributions listed in Table 1 and simultaneously sampled the meteorological inputs from ERA5 data set (Hersbach et al., 2023). The specification of parameter prior distributions follow (Heimsch et al., 2024). In addition, the emulator inputs included the latitude (LAT on Table 1, required for evaluating day length in BASGRA) corresponding to the meteorological sampling point, and site-specific soil properties describing the soil water contents at saturation, field capacity and wilting point (WCST, FWCF, FWCWP on Table 1, respectively). Similar to the model parameters, the soil properties were sampled from uniform distributions.

While the emulator retained the full set of meteorological inputs used by BASGRA, the set of model parameters included in the emulator was reduced to limit the computational cost of training. The parameters were selected using the uncertainty analysis workflow implemented in the Predictive Ecosystem Analyzer (PEcAn; Lebauer et al., 2013). The uncertainty analysis was conducted for three target variables (annual mean GPP, LAI and harvest yield) using the weather inputs and soil properties for the Qvidja site as described in Heimsch et al. (2024), and repeated for 20 different meteorological forcings obtained by sampling individual years from the gridded climatological data set described by Aalto et al. (2016). For each year and target variable, 1000 parameter combinations were sampled using the Sobol method, and the parameters were ranked by the partial variances (the fraction of the total variance attributable to a single parameter). To combine the results we gave each parameter an aggregate score equal to the sum of their inverse ranks in each separate uncertainty analysis, and finally, the 10 highest scoring parameters listed in Table 1 were selected as inputs for the emulator.

The emulator was trained using meteorological driver data extracted from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2023) for the years between 1941 to 2022. The meteorological data were sampled for randomly chosen points within the land area between 35°–72° N and 20° W–60° E. While the emulator was intended for applications in boreal climates, the broader range of temperate and continental climates was intentionally included to improve the emulator's generalizability in both current and future climates. Areas with Mediterranean climates were excluded, for reducing computational time in training since they are too dissimilar. The geographical area is visualized in Figure S1.

We interpolated the ERA5 data from a 0.25° grid to a 0.1° grid with the nearest neighbor method. For latitudes, we used the spacing of 0.1°, and $0.1^\circ \cdot 1/\cos(\phi)$ for longitudes, applying a scaling factor $1/\cos(\phi)$, where ϕ denotes the latitude in radians (Snyder, 1987). The scaling factor is applied to ensure even spacing across the area to avoid over-representing the northern latitudes caused by the convergence of meridians.

The harvest yields are represented in the emulator as a continuous time series with value of zero for the weeks without a harvest, and a value of one for weeks with a harvest. Harvests dates are sampled from three distinct time windows: (1) June, (2) July to August and (3) September to mid-October, which represent a typical management regime for cultivated grasslands in Finland. For each time window, it is randomly determined whether a harvest will occur. In other words, there are different cases in the training data with no harvests, single harvests or multiple harvests (at most three). If a harvest occurs, the harvest day is randomly sampled within the period from a uniform distribution.

We generated the training data from the simulation input–output pairs where daily time series data were averaged to weekly values. Since we target emulating seasonal to yearly time scales, weekly averages are sufficient to capture their dynamics without the need for computationally heavier processing of higher temporal resolution data. Each data point in the training data represents a distinct location (92030 in total) on the geographical area and a one-year period from May to next year's May, selected from the 81-year period.

The training data set was then divided into 5 folds to perform cross-validation for evaluating the emulator's generalization performance. Instead of a fixed train–test split, we employed a 5-fold cross validation where we used a different set for training and testing each time, because this method reduces the risk of overfitting to the specific conditions in the training data and ensures a more robust performance estimation compared to the fixed train–test split approach. Our aim was to train the emulator primarily for use in Finland, therefore temporal generalization to unseen years was necessary rather than generalization to new geographical areas. Furthermore, generalizing the model outside the geographical training domain would require consideration of agricultural practices, such as different harvest windows, that would be beyond the scope of the present work. Thus, the training data was blocked by time but neighboring locations were allowed in separate folds. We defined the folds by dividing the set of locations and time periods randomly to 5 separate subsets. Each of the locations on the whole geographical area was randomly assigned to one fold only, resulting in a division with random scattering throughout the area for each fold. Also, each of the one-year periods (May to May) was assigned to one fold only. Thus, a specific location or a one-year period does not appear in more than one fold. After this division, each location within a fold was randomly assigned one of the time periods assigned to that fold. The same time period can appear in the same fold multiple times paired with a different location (as there are $[92030/5]=18406$ locations in each fold with only $[80/5]=16$ one-year periods to pair with). A robust estimate of the model performance is then computed as the mean of the errors over folds, also assessed by comparing errors between folds to gain insight on whether the emulator generalizes better to specific folds.

Varying the input variables in their given native ranges can lead to variables with larger values dominating the weights of the network, which may not reflect the true relative importance of the variable in producing the desired output. Similarly, the differing ranges of the output variables may lead to unstable training process due to inconsistent gradient scales. Therefore, in order to ensure the equal treatment of each input variable and a stable training process, we standardized both input and output data separately within each fold to have the mean of zero and standard deviation of one with the formula $x_i^* = \frac{x_i - \mu_i}{\sigma_i}$, where x_i^* denotes the new rescaled variables, μ_i and σ_i represent the mean and the standard deviation of the variable within the training set of each fold, respectively.

Table 1

Model inputs, parameters and outputs: The table lists model inputs, including meteorological data and harvest dates, followed by model parameters, and lastly model outputs. The units specified for each component correspond to units used in the emulator.

Model input	Description	Unit	Source
<i>air_temperature</i>	Air temperature	K	ERA5
<i>relative_humidity</i>	Relative humidity	%	ERA5
<i>surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air</i>	Flux of solar radiation reaching the surface	W m ⁻²	ERA5
<i>precipitation_flux</i>	Precipitation flux	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	ERA5
<i>wind_speed</i>	Wind speed	m s ⁻¹	ERA5
<i>harvest_day</i>	Harvest days	–	Random sampling described in text
Model parameter	Description	Unit	Distribution
<i>LAICR</i>	LAI above which shading induces leaf senescence	m ² m ⁻²	Uniform(2.0, 7.0)
<i>LAIEFT</i>	Decrease in tillering with leaf area index	m ² m ⁻²	Uniform(0.1, 0.35)
<i>LAITIL</i>	Maximum ratio of tiller and leaf appearance at low leaf area index	–	Uniform(0.30, 1.10)
<i>NELVM</i>	Number of elongating leaves per non-elongating tiller	tiller ⁻¹	Uniform(1.0, 2.75)
<i>PHY</i>	Phyllochron	°C d	LogNormal(4.25, 0.25)
<i>ROOTDM</i>	Initial and maximum value rooting depth	m	Uniform(0.50, 1.50)
<i>RUBISC</i>	Rubisco content of upper leaves	g m ⁻²	Uniform(1.0, 10.0)
<i>SHAPE</i>	Area of a leaf relative to a rectangle of the same length and width	–	Beta(4.0, 2.0)
<i>TBASE</i>	Minimum value of effective temperature for leaf elongation	°C	Uniform(3.0, 10.0)
<i>TCRES</i>	Time constant of mobilization of reserves	d	Uniform(1.0, 3.0)
<i>LAT</i>	Latitude	°N	–
<i>FWCFC</i>	Water content at field capacity relative to saturation	–	Uniform(0.1, 0.9)
<i>WCST</i>	Water concentration at saturation	m ³ m ⁻³	Uniform(0.1, 0.9)
<i>FWCWP</i>	Fraction of water content at wilting point	–	Uniform(0.1× <i>FWCFC</i> , 0.9× <i>FWCFC</i>)
Model output	Description	Unit	
LAI	Leaf area index	m ² m ⁻²	
NPP	Net primary production	g C m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
GPP	Gross primary production	g C m ⁻² h ⁻¹	
Soil moisture	Soil moisture	kg m ⁻²	
Harvest carbon flux	Harvest carbon flux	g C m ⁻² d ⁻¹	

2.2.2. Neural network components

We used a combination of Feed-forward neural networks (FNN) and Long short-term memory networks (LSTM) to build the emulator. LSTMs are recurrent neural networks, which iteratively produce an output for each time step, whereas FNNs learn representations in data without sequential structure. They typically consist of multiple stacked layers enabling hierarchical learning, each layer capturing progressively refined patterns. In our case, FNNs further learn patterns from

the representations of the LSTM outputs, integrating all the relevant information to produce the final prediction, as described below in further detail.

LSTM, proposed by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997), is a type of recurrent neural network, which is designed to learn both long-term and short-term dependencies in data, by adding recurrent connections to its units (a.k.a. cells). The LSTM structure introduces a gate mechanism inside the cells enabling the model to sufficiently capture

long-term dependencies. In addition to the hidden state, LSTMs introduce a cell state to store long-term information. A cell comprises three gates, all of which filter the information moving between the cells and states: 1) the forget gate, introduced by Gers et al. (1999), learns to forget old irrelevant information from the cell state; 2) the input gate learns to filter out the irrelevant input from coming to the cell state; 3) the output gate learns to filter out the currently irrelevant information stored in the cell state from the hidden state. The LSTM cell employed the standard activation functions, σ for the gate mechanism and \tanh for the activation of the cell input.

LSTM outputs are then integrated and refined by an FNN. FNNs consist of one or more hidden layers, which are connected in a sequential chain of functions (Goodfellow et al., 2016). All FNN layers were applied with a ReLU (rectified linear unit) activation function, except for the final layer as no bounded output range was defined.

2.2.3. Emulator hyperparameter optimization and training

After defining the neural network components and the training data, we performed hyperparameter optimization by training the model (i.e. the emulator, throughout this section) with multiple settings to find the optimal model configuration. Neural network models involve multiple hyperparameters, including number and size of layers and parameters regarding to the training process. Our goal was to find an accurate model with relatively low computational time.

We trained and tested the alternative models with python, using the Flax library and the Optax library for the training algorithm. We used the Adam algorithm, a stochastic gradient descent method with adaptive learning rates, as the neural network training algorithm, to iteratively optimize the weights of the network (Kingma and Ba, 2017). With each model configuration we performed 5-fold cross validation for estimating the performance, in order to choose the best performing model architecture.

We applied Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) (Bergstra et al., 2011), a computationally fast Bayesian algorithm, through the Optuna library (Akiba et al., 2019) to find the optimal hyperparameters for our model. TPE uses Gaussian mixture models to estimate the probability density functions for hyperparameters yielding to the best objective values $l(x)$ and the remaining points $g(x)$. The next hyperparameter values are then decided by maximizing the ratio $l(x)/g(x)$. The mean error over folds was used to assess the model performance and estimate the best performing hyperparameters. First, we defined a hyperparameter space, listed in Table 2, with changing order and size for the neural network components. We tested multiple options for the optimal LSTM-layer positioning, and determined whether the input data could pass through the first layer directly or if it should go through FNN-filtering first. Also other hyperparameters, such as the learning rate for the Adam algorithm, batch size, epoch size and dropout rate were optimized.

Next, we used the TPE algorithm to search for the optimal values in the hyperparameter space. We divided the search into two separate searches, with two alternative designs. The first search applied the LSTM-layer only to the sequential input and processed the model parameters by zero (no processing) to two FNN-layers. The processed sequential input and parameters were then concatenated and lastly filtered by one to two FNN-layers to produce the final output. The second search concatenated the parameters and the sequential input before any parameter layers. Then, the concatenated input was filtered by zero to two FNN-layers, a LSTM-layer and then again processed by one to two FNN-layers to produce the final output. Both setups were given 150 trials for the TPE algorithm, as the performance of either search did not improve during the last one-tenth of the trials. Also an early stopping criteria was implemented in the process which had a patience of 3 iterations of not significant improvement. A significant improvement in this context was defined as a reduction of at least $1e^{-4}$ in the mean RMSE across folds, calculated with the normalized predictions.

The second search, with both the model parameters and the sequential inputs passing directly through the LSTM-layer, resulted in lower RMSE. The architectures with fewer layers seemed to perform better comparing to more complex architectures. The TPE-optimized architecture, visualized in Fig. 1, includes first concatenating the sequential and static inputs together, such that each time step's input vector is merged with the static input. Then the concatenated input goes through the LSTM-layer, and two regular FNN-layers, the last one giving the final output. The optimized values for the hyperparameters are listed in Table 2. The size of the final layer is fixed at 5 corresponding to the estimated output variables (LAI, NPP, GPP, soil moisture and harvest carbon flux) and was not included in the optimization.

After the TPE optimization, the set of best performing parameters were used to train the final emulator, shown in Algorithm S1.

2.3. Emulator-based Bayesian calibration

2.3.1. Study sites

After building, optimizing and training the emulator, we applied it to three study sites in boreal and hemi-boreal climate zones across Finland where we used eddy-covariance tower flux measurements to perform an emulator-based Bayesian calibration. The location, soil texture and measured time period for each site are presented in Table 3. In total, we had 8 one-year periods to calibrate and validate the emulator, with each site managed as a temporary grassland during these years. Only exception is Viikki where the simulation period overlapped with bare soil conditions, due to the field being tilled in November 2022 in preparation of sowing cereal based mixture in May 2023.

The GPP data stream used in calibration was derived from half-hourly CO_2 fluxes measured using the eddy covariance method. A detailed description of the sites, instrumentation and data processing is given in Vira et al. (2025); further details of the Qvidja and Ruukki sites are given in Heimsch et al. (2024) and Gerin et al. (2023). We chose GPP as a constraint for calibration as it is a central component in ecosystem carbon balance and is more directly accessible from the measurements compared to NPP, which would require additional information on plant respiration. In order to calibrate the emulator against the GPP data, the data was averaged to weekly values ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$).

For each site, also the LAI data was obtained in order to analyze the predictive performance of LAI after calibration against GPP data. The LAI values were estimated from Sentinel-2 observations as described by Nevalainen et al. (2022). The LAI data contains some missing values, which were not gap-filled. LAI data was also averaged to weekly means, ignoring the missing values, in order to facilitate the evaluation of the calibrated model's performance in LAI estimation. For the same purpose, we obtained harvest carbon flux data from harvest biomass data, which was collected from the site managers and available for most of the harvests.

2.3.2. Calibration protocol

We employed a Bayesian approach to perform parameter calibration on the emulator, applying the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method to iteratively construct a Markov chain converging to the target distribution. However, traditional MCMC techniques, such as Metropolis–Hastings, struggle at exploring high-dimensional parameter spaces efficiently due to their semi-random walk behavior (using a proposal distribution conditioned upon the last iteration). To address this, Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) methods that utilize gradient information of the posterior distribution for taking new steps in the parameter space are proposed, enabling more efficient exploring of the parameter space (Duane et al., 1987). We chose to use a variant of HMC, specifically the No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) which adaptively tunes the step size and decides the number of leap frog steps, eliminating the need of hand-tuning these hyperparameters (Hoffman and

Table 2
Hyperparameter search space and TPE-optimized values, with dropout rate having a step size of 0.01.

Hyperparameter	Search space	Optimized value
1st FNN-layer	[True, False]	False
2nd FNN-layer	[True, False]	False
3rd FNN-layer	[True, False]	True
hidden size of 1st FNN-layer	$[20, 400] \in \mathbb{Z}$	–
hidden size of 2nd FNN-layer	$[20, 400] \in \mathbb{Z}$	–
hidden size of 3rd FNN-layer	$[20, 400] \in \mathbb{Z}$	211
hidden size of LSTM-layer	$[20, 400] \in \mathbb{Z}$	162
dropout rate	$[0, 0.75] \in \mathbb{R}$	0.06
batch size	$[10, 100] \in \mathbb{Z}$	83
learning rate	$[0.001, 0.01]$	0.001

Fig. 1. Final emulator architecture: The emulator receives a vector p , consisting of model parameters, and vectors m_1, \dots, m_T consisting of the meteorological variables for each of the T time steps. For each time step i the vectors p and m_i are concatenated and passed to the LSTM cell as an input, which generates a (T, n_1) dimensional output. Next, this output goes through a Dense-layer as an input, which in return generates an output of size (T, n_2) that finally passes through the last Dense-layer, producing the prediction of size $(T, n_3 = 5)$.

Table 3
Grassland sites used in this study.

Site name	Location	Time period	Soil texture
Qvidja	60.30°N, 22.39°E	May 2018–May 2023	clay loam
Ruukki	64.42°N, 25.00°E	May 2020–May 2022	peat
Viikki	60.22°N, 25.02°E	May 2022–May 2023	clay loam

Gelman, 2014). We used the NUTS implementation in the Numpyro library (Phan et al., 2019).

We assume the residual error follows a Gaussian distribution, with mean μ equal to model prediction and standard deviation σ simultaneously fitted during the calibration process. The likelihood function is given by

$$p(y|\theta) = \prod_{i=1}^N \mathcal{N}(y_i, \mu, \sigma) = \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(y_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right),$$

where y denotes the observations, y_i and μ_i denote the observed and predicted values for data point i , respectively, N is the number of observations, and θ represents the model parameters being calibrated.

For the statistical data model (likelihood) error term, σ , we used a standard weakly informative prior InverseGamma($\alpha = 1, \beta = 1$), reflecting minimal assumption on the variability in the data.

The calibration process involved 10 parameters related to vegetation growth, with prior distributions same as the ones listed in Table 1, except for the rubisco content parameter (*RUBISC*). We derived the *RUBISC* prior from grassland leaf nitrogen measurement data provided by the TRY database (TRY File Archive, 2019; Gubsch et al., 2010). We obtained rubisco content values from the nitrogen measurements, to which we then fitted a log-normal normal distribution, resulting in a prior distribution of LogNormal($\mu = 0.95, \sigma = 0.66$). We deemed the previous *RUBISC* range (Uniform[1, 10]), from which the emulator training data was sampled, not suitable for reflecting realistic variations

Table 4

Calibration experiments: first column lists the data used in calibration, second column lists the test data and whether it is in-sample or out-of-sample, third column # lists the number of experiments corresponding to the setup of each row, fourth column gives one example setup and last column lists the figures where the performance of each setup is shown.

Calibration data	Test data	#	Example	Figure
All sites and years	All site-year pairs (in-sample)	8	Calibrated with all years from Qvidja, Ruukki and Viikki, tested with Qvidja 2020	Fig. 4
Site n with all years (for n in sites)	All site n -year pairs (in-sample)	8	Calibrated with all Qvidja years, tested with Qvidja 2020	Figs. 4, 7, 8
Site n with all years (for n in sites)	All site m -year pairs with $n \neq m$ (out-of-sample)	16	Calibrated with all Ruukki years, tested with Qvidja 2020	Figs. 4, 7, 8
Site n with year y (for n, y in sites, years)	Site n with year y (in-sample)	8	Calibrated with Qvidja 2020, tested with Qvidja 2020	Figs. 5, S4
Site n with all years except year y (for y in years in site n)	Site n with year y (out-of-sample)	7	Calibrated with all Qvidja years except 2020, tested with Qvidja 2020	Figs. 5, S4
Sites n and m with all years (for n, m in sites)	All site-year pairs in n and m (in-sample)	16	Calibrated with all Qvidja and Ruukki years, tested with Qvidja 2020	Fig. 4
Sites n and m with all years (for n, m in sites)	All site-year pairs outside n and m (out-of-sample)	8	Calibrated with all Viikki and Ruukki years, tested with Qvidja 2020	Figs. 5, S4

in rubisco content whereas the log-normal prior distribution provides a more biologically representative characterization, with a high density around 2 g/m^2 .

Before applying the calibration at the sites, we first performed a synthetic data experiment to test our emulator-based calibration protocol. In this experiment, we first ran the simulator (BASGRA) with a parameter vector randomly sampled from the parameter prior distributions to generate the synthetic observation. To better reflect the noise in actual measurement data, we added some Gaussian noise to the simulator outputs. Next, we performed the calibration, with the detailed protocol above, using this synthetic observation. We then compared the resulting posteriors to the known (“true”) simulator parameter values that generated the data. After the synthetic data experiment, we performed calibrations with data from different combinations of sites and years, and analyzed their performance on both the in-sample data (i.e. the data calibration has seen) and on out-of-sample data from other sites and years (i.e. the data calibration has not seen). All resulting 71 experiments are listed in Table 4.

We evaluate the model performance in the calibration experiments with root mean squared error where squared differences between predictions and observations are first summed over ensemble members and time steps. This way of calculating the error simultaneously measures the skill of the mean prediction and the error quantification given by the ensemble spread (Leung et al., 2021). Under simplified assumptions, this metric can be shown to approximate the Continuous ranked probability score (Leung et al., 2021), a commonly used proper scoring rule (Gneiting and Raftery, 2007) for probabilistic forecasts. Additionally, we calculated the normalized root mean squared error to evaluate the model performance by scaling the error over the range of each variable, providing a ratio that relates the error to the variability of the data. Further, we evaluated the coefficient of determination, which is a commonly used metric to quantify a model’s ability to reproduce the variability in the data.

In total, for each calibration setup we ran 10 000 iterations, with the initial 2000 iterations serving as a burn-in period. We monitored the convergence of the sampler by examining the trace plots and Gelman–Rubin statistic \hat{R} . In all calibrations presented in this study, the \hat{R} values

were below 1.005. The computational time of each calibration ranges from under 3 min to 16 min using a single CPU core (Intel Xeon Gold 6230, 2.1 GHz) on the Puhti supercomputer operated by the Finland’s Center for Scientific Computing CSC.

3. Results

3.1. Emulator performance after training

We evaluated the emulator predictive performance for each variable, including LAI, NPP, GPP, soil moisture and harvest carbon flux, individually. To obtain a robust estimate for the emulator performance we performed 5 fold cross validation where the performance of each trained model was evaluated with root mean squared error (RMSE), normalized RMSE (NRMSE) and coefficient of determination R^2 on the corresponding test fold, listed in Table 5. There was no significant variability observed between the fold performances. Based on the cross validation, we estimate the emulator to be able to explain over 96% of the variation of LAI simulations, over 95% of NPP, over 96% of GPP simulations, over 98% of soil moisture and over 98% for harvest carbon simulations. The final emulator gave a mean normalized RMSE (NRMSE) of 0.013 for the training set and 0.017 for the test set across folds.

Due to the negligible differences between performance across folds, we present only the performance of the first fold in the following figures. Fig. 2 shows variations in performance between seasons of the simulation year. We divided the simulation period into four seasons (in regard to Finland specific context); early growing season (May–July), late growing season (August–October), early winter (November–January) and early spring (February–April), and compared the predictive performances of each predicted variable across the seasons in Fig. 2. The figure shows predicted values per each season, and lists the performance metrics for the corresponding seasons. R^2 values were over 0.94 for every time period and variable, including LAI, NPP, GPP and soil moisture.

For LAI, NPP and GPP, the performance across seasons shows similar patterns, as these predicted variables are all closely related; we

Table 5
Emulator performance over folds.

Variable	Metric	Fold 1	Fold 2	Fold 3	Fold 4	Fold 5	Mean
LAI (m ² m ⁻²)	R ²	0.972	0.973	0.968	0.973	0.967	0.971
	RMSE	0.216	0.212	0.227	0.213	0.230	0.220
	NRMSE	0.021	0.021	0.023	0.021	0.023	0.022
NPP (g C m ⁻² h ⁻¹)	R ²	0.957	0.958	0.954	0.958	0.953	0.956
	RMSE	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.021	0.020
	NRMSE	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.025	0.024
GPP (g C m ⁻² h ⁻¹)	R ²	0.963	0.964	0.960	0.964	0.960	0.962
	RMSE	0.039	0.038	0.040	0.039	0.040	0.039
	NRMSE	0.025	0.025	0.026	0.025	0.026	0.026
Soil Moisture (kg m ⁻²)	R ²	0.984	0.986	0.985	0.985	0.984	0.985
	RMSE	17.508	16.518	16.866	16.761	17.331	16.997
	NRMSE	0.017	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.017	0.016
Harvest Carbon (g C m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	R ²	0.985	0.986	0.983	0.985	0.983	0.984
	RMSE	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016
	NRMSE	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005

Fig. 2. LAI, NPP, GPP and soil moisture predictive performances across different seasons of the year.

Fig. 3. Harvest carbon flux predictions on harvest-only weeks.

see higher RMSE during the whole growing season compared to early winter, which tends to increase with higher predicted values (Fig. 2). Yet, R^2 is over 0.96 for the whole growing season. Conversely, soil moisture gets more dispersed around the identity line, with higher error on colder months, which may be due to the difficulties of the simulator to model values for frozen soil and producing a clear pattern for the emulator to learn. For all of the four predicted variables, the performance on early spring (Feb–Apr) is lower compared to the other periods, with the lowest values for R^2 .

Even though we designed the model to estimate harvest carbon flux for all time steps, we included only the meaningful values (with occurring harvests) in the calculations of the evaluation metrics, as the harvest days are already known and non-harvest weeks can be masked out. The model performance for the harvest-only weeks, as illustrated in Fig. 3, indicates good performance.

3.2. Emulator performance after calibration

The synthetic data experiment, where GPP simulated by BASGRA with randomly chosen parameter values was used in calibration, successfully recovered the true parameter values for parameters contributing to GPP (e.g. *RUBISC*, *ROOTDM*) (Figure S3). Other parameters (e.g. *LAICR*, *LAIEFT*) have wider posteriors, close to their priors, due to their weak contribution to GPP prediction. This exercise demonstrates the applicability of our emulator-based calibration protocol to real-world data as reported below. In all of the real-world calibration setups listed in Table 4, post-calibration emulator outperformed the pre-calibration in predictive performance (Fig. 4).

Fig. 5 shows the calibration performance with in-sample and out-of-sample test data at Qvidja: the first column has the performance for a specific year with parameters calibrated with the same site's and year's data (in-sample), second column's parameters are calibrated with same site data but excluding the test year (out-of-sample year), and the third column has parameters calibrated with other sites' data (out-of-sample site). A similar figure but for Ruukki and Viikki sites is provided in the supplement (Figure S4). When tested at a specific year, there is no significant difference between the calibration using other Qvidja years and the calibration using other sites (Fig. 5, second versus third column). However, this is not the case for Ruukki, where the cross-year calibration performs considerably worse than the cross-site calibration

(Figure S4, second versus third column). As expected, year-specific calibration (in-sample, Fig. 5 and S4, first column) shows the best agreement when tested at that year (i.e. against the data calibration has seen).

Likely due to the initialization setup, the calibrated emulator has difficulties in capturing the steep increase of the observed GPP in the early weeks for some Qvidja years such as 2021 (Fig. 5, fourth row). However, a similar steep increase in the Ruukki data is well matched after the calibration (Figure S4). The difference between the sites is that the observed GPP values for the first time steps are near zero for Ruukki and at around $0.2 \text{ (g C m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}\text{)}$ for the initial time step for all years from Qvidja. In other words, the growing season has already progressed by the start of the simulation at Qvidja, for which the emulator lags behind and struggles to capture the transient dynamic under the current modeling protocol. Conversely the situation in Ruukki is well within the training parameters and limits of the emulator.

The second and the fourth year of the Qvidja data show the poorest performance across all calibrations in Fig. 4. This is also visible in Fig. 5, where both of the years have notably high values for observed GPP at the early time steps which end up falling outside of the posterior intervals. Also the GPP values for March and April are overestimated by the posterior. The use of Ruukki data in calibration results in higher RMSE compared to the other subsets used in calibration in Fig. 4. The performance is affected by the first year of Ruukki data which has notably higher values, with highest GPP value reaching nearly $0.9 \text{ (g C m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}\text{)}$, whereas the other sites and years have maximum values below $0.75 \text{ (g C m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}\text{)}$. As a result, when calibrated with Ruukki 2020, the model underestimates the GPP values of Ruukki 2021 (Figure S4). The Ruukki 2021 GPP values were similarly underestimated when non-Ruukki years were used in calibration. Conversely, the model overestimates the values for Ruukki 2020 when Ruukki 2021 was used in calibration. For Viikki, the model performs similarly when calibrated on only Viikki data versus on data from all other sites and years.

Posterior distributions for each calibrated parameter for different calibration setups are presented in Fig. 6. The rooting depth (*ROOTDM*) varies significantly across the calibrations, and has a bimodal distribution when calibrated with Ruukki 2020 data. Similarly, the *NELVM* and *TBASE* (parameters controlling leaf development) and *RUBISC* (leaf rubisco content) posteriors have more variation between calibrations than the other parameters. By comparison, other parameters' posteriors show a general alignment across the calibrations. All posteriors for *sigma* encompass smaller values than the prior.

The LAI predictions were also constrained by calibration with GPP. Fig. 7 shows LAI predictions for each year and site, when calibrated with the same site and all the available years for that site. The calibrated model seems to overestimate LAI right after harvests. For example, after the first harvest of 2018 in Qvidja (first row and column in Fig. 7) the LAI value drops near to zero in the observed LAI data, while the model estimates the LAI values to drop only to over half of the value just before harvest. As the calibration in Fig. 7 includes all years of the corresponding site, there is a certain degree of compensation between the years where the posterior underestimates the LAI values for Qvidja 2019 while overestimating Qvidja 2022.

Fig. 8 compares the observed and predicted harvest carbon fluxes when the calibration is performed either with site-year-specific data (fourth row in Table 4) or with all available years from the specific site (second row in Table 4). Based on the RMSEs (Table 6), the model calibrated with year-specific data performs best for almost all Ruukki harvests and a few Qvidja harvests. When calibrated with all site-specific years, the model shows best performance for most of the Qvidja harvests. For Viikki and last year of Ruukki, the prior performs better compared to either of the posteriors. The largest model-data mismatches occur for highest harvest carbon values, such as the first harvest of 2020 in Ruukki and first and only harvest of 2021 in Qvidja. We note that these harvest values fall outside of the prior range as well, and the agreement does not show much variation before and after the calibration.

Fig. 4. RMSE ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) values from experiments using all site-year pairs as test data, and all possible site combinations and all available years as calibration data. Q stands for Qvidja, R for Ruukki and V for Viikki. For “Q all” and “R all”, the RMSE value represents the mean across all years.

4. Discussion

4.1. Emulator

4.1.1. Emulator protocol and training data

Based on the performance comparison between seasons (Fig. 2), the accuracy of the emulator decreased rapidly for most of the predicted variables (LAI, GPP, NPP) towards the end of the simulation period, with worst performance on early spring. Similar behavior is shown in Figure S2 where the error increases significantly when approaching the last few time steps. The variance in model performance in time can be partly explained by seasonal dynamics. In the case of plant-related variables, the emulator might not accurately capture the processes (e.g. mobilization of reserve carbon pools) that control vegetation regrowth after overwintering, since the training loss is likely dominated by the growing-season dynamics. The RMSE behaves differently for soil moisture, for which the increase of the error starts already in autumn, which can be due to the difficulties for the simulator to model frozen soil and create a clear pattern for the emulator to learn. Furthermore, the relevant time scales for soil moisture might differ by the season, as more precipitation and evaporation happens during summer, and thus, in summer the soil moisture could be driven by shorter term temporal dependencies than over the winter. Since LSTMs apply the same trained parameters at each time step, the emulator might have difficulties in modeling seasonally varying temporal dependencies.

The rapid increase of RMSE for LAI, GPP and NPP could also be partially explained by the transmission of data over many time steps, as LSTM’s capacity to remember long-term dependencies is limited by the architecture and training of the model (Al-Selwi et al., 2023). Thus, some of the long-term information may be forgotten, possibly leading to accumulating errors over time steps (Cai et al., 2021). A possible approach to mitigate information loss over long periods is to apply Transformer neural networks (Vaswani et al., 2023), which process the entire input sequence using standard FNNs, instead of processing it one time step at a time. Transformers are effective in learning long-term dependencies in sequential data, by only using attention mechanisms. These models could be applicable in emulation and process the time sequence in parallel, however, they can be deep, and require more trained parameters, which increase the risk of overfitting and slower convergence in training. Nevertheless, the LSTM emulator showed strong performance in the growing season, which is the most active and crucial phase in carbon dynamics.

Prediction of harvest carbon flux closely follows the simulator’s behavior for the weeks with harvest, see Fig. 3. Non-harvest weeks have a value of zero for the harvest carbon, as there are no harvests happening. Although the zero values are distinct, they may still be challenging for a neural network to learn exactly, like any other specific target. However, since the harvest dates are already known, the weeks with no harvest can be masked out. Dropping the time step dimension would be another way for creating the harvest carbon flux output, where only 3 values, one for each harvest time window, would give the harvest carbon output per simulation instead of $T = 53$ (weeks). This method would have required more layers in the network, inflicting more computational costs for training and hyperparameter optimization. Since the post-processing was relatively straightforward, we chose the simpler and more efficient architecture.

The hyperparameter search and validation of the predictive performance of the emulator was performed simultaneously with cross validation, which implies that the optimized hyperparameters are in part informed by the data assigned to the test sets. However, the data leakage is expected to be minimal due to the use of mean RMSE over all folds for the hyperparameter search and the large size and diversity of the data. Nevertheless, there is a potential optimistic bias in the performance estimates. We note, however, that the robustness of the cross-validation could be improved even further by withholding part of the data from the hyperparameter search for the final validation.

Dividing the training data into 5 folds, each containing distinct temporal and geographical subsets of the training data, demonstrates how the emulator generalizes to new data. Each of the trained fold had a similar predictive performance and generalized well to the test data, with small difference between test and train RMSE, indicating good generalization over the years. However, since we did not follow a spatial blocking design in creating the folds and the emulator has certain practical assumptions (e.g. on growing season and harvesting regime) the emulator cannot be expected to generalize well to locations outside the applied geographical area.

The geographical area included in the meteorological training data covered nearly all Europe instead of being limited to Finland. This approach introduced variability to the training data, which might help performing also in extreme weather conditions, when applied to Finland. Since we were mainly concerned with variability for the purpose of training the emulator, we also deemed the ERA5 dataset to be befitting for the inputs. However, we note that one can swap different products as inputs, such as the downscaled ERA5-Land dataset

Fig. 5. Calibration performance comparison for Quidja site with different calibration data sets. The observed GPP is shown as the dark blue line, the gray area shows the 95% highest density interval of the prior GPP predictions and the light blue area shows the 95% highest posterior density interval. The harvest events are denoted by vertical lines.

or in situ measurements, as the LSTM-FNN is flexible in adapting to diverse meteorological drivers. Despite this effort for generality, we acknowledge that future scenarios can still fall outside the variability present in the training data, for example scenarios driven by weather extremes caused by climate change or new agricultural practices. While some aspects of the emulator, such as the three harvest windows, currently limit its generalization outside boreal regions, the geographically even cross-validation performance suggests that the current procedure could be followed to train an emulator applicable to a wider range of climatic and management conditions.

The emulator's predictive performance is potentially affected by the restricted amount of model parameters included in the training. We performed an uncertainty analysis to select the most contributing parameters in prediction of all variables combined, thus some parameters that are influential for only a specific output variable can possibly be missing. However, many of the emulated variables are closely related,

and parameters contributing to one variable often also contribute to another variable, which may reduce the number of parameters to adequately sample the model uncertainty.

4.1.2. Neural network architecture optimization

Neural network training and optimization of their hyperparameters can be computationally heavy, particularly with increasing amount of training data and complexity of the hyperparameter space. We chose the Bayesian TPE approach for hyperparameter optimization because more classical optimization methods, such as grid search and random search, either require smaller hyperparameter space with good guesses or inefficient searches without using prior knowledge in parameter selection. The TPE algorithm required only under 150 trials for both sub-searches, with distinct structures, of the 2.3×10^{15} possible predefined combinations, to find optimal values for the hyperparameters. The resulting architecture was relatively simple with only two layers outside

Fig. 6. Posterior distributions for the calibrated parameters, with rows representing different calibration data sets. For better visualization, the shown ranges for *sigma*, *PHY* and *RUBISC* are narrower than the full priors, where densities are negligible outside the shown ranges.

the LSTM-layer with 152 977 trained parameters (weights and biases) in total, while the TPE search allowed for a maximum of 1 140 005 parameters. Thus, the hyperparameter optimization implies a smaller model to be sufficient for our task, while larger models could have been more prone to overfitting.

The first hyperparameter set proposed by the TPE algorithm was chosen as random because of no prior knowledge of the effect of any hyperparameter values on the model performance. The first trial, corresponding to the first proposed hyperparameter set, included a large dropout rate, smaller size for the LSTM-layer and two additional layers for processing the model parameters, yielding to a test RMSE of 0.1618 evaluated for normalized training data. In contrast, the optimized hyperparameter set yielded an RMSE value of 0.0247. This demonstrates the influence of model architecture and the need to carefully define a hyperparameter space covering a wide range of values. Testing all the possible hyperparameter combinations would have been possible for a significantly smaller hyperparameter space, requiring strong prior constraints for the values. The TPE algorithm allows for the selection of wider ranges and more values in the hyperparameter space, reducing the need for manual tuning. The hyperparameter space defined in this study could have been expanded further to explore even larger ranges, as by increasing the size or number of layers, the representational capacity of the emulator increases (Goodfellow et al., 2016). However, the TPE optimized hyperparameters gave a rather simple network, and the hidden sizes were not hitting the specified limits, thus we did not see a reason to expand the space. This enabled also faster convergence of the TPE algorithm.

Another approach for building the emulator structure could have been incorporating knowledge on the structure of the process-based

model, which is built based on theory of the biological processes. Liu et al. (2024) employed this method to build a hierarchically structured knowledge-guided neural network model incorporating knowledge from a process-based model based on ecosystem theory of carbon allocation. While incorporating knowledge on the internal structure might present some other advantages such as interpretability, this approach would involve a much more complex network which would be less straightforward to implement and train.

Overall, the emulator building process with architecture optimization and the following calibration is expected to be applicable to other process-based models with similar processes. Emulating variables that evolve on longer time scales, such as soil organic carbon, might raise challenges in our setup, and could be mitigated by lengthening the simulation period. However, when increasing the number of time steps, the model's predictive performance might suffer due to LSTM's capacity to remember dependencies over large number of time steps. When applied to another process-based model, the training data would be similarly obtained from the model simulations and the hyperparameter space would be defined accordingly, with possibly more layers for more complex relationships, also depending on the number and characteristics of the input–output pairs. Expanding the hyperparameter space, could lead to slower convergence of the TPE algorithm.

4.2. Calibration

The HMC NUTS algorithm efficiently converged to the posteriors in only 10 000 iterations. In comparison to MCMC Metropolis algorithm (Metropolis et al., 1953), which was previously used in

Fig. 7. LAI predictions per site after calibration with data from all site-specific years. The blue dots show the LAI observations, gray area shows the 95% highest density interval for the prior LAI predictions and the pink shows the 95% highest posterior density interval.

Fig. 8. Harvest carbon flux predictions for each year and site with posteriors calibrated with site-specific data from all years (dark blue) and with site-year-specific data (green). See Table 6 for corresponding RMSE values.

Table 6

RMSE values ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) for harvest carbon predictions in Fig. 8, with prior (Pr), posterior when calibrated with all site-specific years (A), and posterior calibrated with site-year-specific data (Y). The last column shows the mean over all sites, years and harvests. The lowest RMSE-value per each harvest is marked in blue. No data was available for the second harvest (H2) in 2018 for Qvidja.

	Qvidja						Ruukki				Viikki	Mean		
	2018		2019		2020		2021	2022	2020		2021		2022	All
	H1	H3	H1	H2	H1	H2	H1	H1	H1	H2	H1	H2	H1	All
Pr	49.99	49.99	103.50	119.57	48.30	103.76	151.08	57.51	89.00	63.16	149.84	65.30	74.98	86.61
A	23.18	6.79	90.12	16.40	27.54	4.62	141.61	21.45	92.07	97.10	158.81	94.33	78.77	65.60
Y	36.53	33.39	81.51	33.45	23.86	40.35	146.43	18.79	72.39	61.04	144.97	78.00	78.77	65.34

calibration of BASGRA (Höglind et al., 2020; Persson et al., 2024), the NUTS algorithm applied to the BASGRA-emulator used only 1/30 to 1/100 of the number of iterations in the mentioned studies, overall clocking 3 to 16 min per calibration experiment. The standard MCMC samplers, such as Metropolis, can result in bad mixing and slow convergence if implemented poorly (Andrieu et al., 2003). NUTS, on the other hand, does not require hand-tuning and iteratively extends the trajectory, halting before redundant exploration of the same regions. The step size is dynamically adapted ensuring more effective exploration of the parameter space. While the computational overhead in NUTS is dominated by the cost of computing gradients, its ability to adaptively tune the trajectory, enables efficient Bayesian posterior inference on high-dimensional models (Hoffman and Gelman, 2014). By employing a differentiable NN emulator in this study, we were able to leverage these advantages of the HMC NUTS algorithm.

BASGRA was also calibrated with a GP emulator previously (Heimsch et al., 2024). 100 000 MCMC iterations with this GP emulator approximately took 16 min (unpublished data), which is comparable towards the higher end of the calibration durations we have seen with the LSTM-FNN emulator in this study. However, we note that this GP emulator-based calibration in Heimsch et al. (2024) was concerned with 4 BASGRA parameters only and trained with 320 design (training) points, compared to the 10 parameters targeted in this study. To better approximate the model for 10 parameters, the GP emulator would have needed to be trained on a lot more (e.g. a conservative estimate of 600–800) design points and scaled poorly per the implementation described in Fer et al. (2018). Besides, this GP-emulator was constructed on the likelihood surface with no time-series dimension, unlike the LSTM-FNN emulator which was shown to be capable of emulating process-based model time-series outputs in this study. Last but not least, the use of the GP emulator was limited to the MCMC algorithm as it was not differentiable unlike the LSTM-FNN emulator.

The performance of the calibrated model was affected by the varying amounts of available data for each site. When the calibration data includes data from multiple sites, the 5-years of data from Qvidja dominate the calibration. This is evident from RMSE values in Fig. 4 which shows similar performance across calibration setups that include all Qvidja data. Not only the amount, but also the characteristics of data affected the calibration outcomes. For example, the second year (2021) in Ruukki had a much higher GPP, reaching a value of 0.89 ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) at maximum, while other sites' GPP values stay under 0.75 ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$). Likely because of this, the year 2021 in Ruukki performs poorly when calibration uses data from other sites and years (Supplement S4). The single year from the Viikki site shows similar performance between the site-year-specific calibration and the cross-site calibration. Both of these calibration experiments show a model-data mismatch in April, where the calibrated model overestimates the GPP values. Furthermore, the observed values in April are significantly lower compared to Qvidja, despite the sites being at close latitudes. In reality, the Viikki site was tilled in November 2022 in preparation of sowing a cereal based mixture in May 2023. The May–May calibration period therefore partly overlapped with bare soil conditions, while the model continued to presume grassland dynamics and failed to account for the change in land use, which is expected, as the emulator was trained for grasslands.

The choice of the simulation start and end points affected the model performance in general. The training simulations were initialized on May 1st each year, and run for 12 months. Especially in Qvidja, this excluded the first weeks of the growing season on some years and sites. The plant carbon pools in BASGRA were given fixed, low initial values, the emulator seems to underestimate the values of GPP in the initial time steps, seen in Fig. 5. Expanding the simulation period to start a few months earlier would improve the emulator performance over the early growing season. However, the May-to-May period was chosen based on Finland's growing season, which starts rather late compared to southern regions of the training domain. Alternatively, the initial

plant carbon pools could be included in building and calibrating the emulator analogously to the model parameters.

Based on the uncertainty analysis, *RUBISC* (leaf rubisco content) is the most contributing parameter in GPP prediction, followed by *ROOTDM* (rooting depth), which explains their narrow posteriors when calibrated with data from all sites and years (Fig. 6). The wider posterior distributions of some of the parameters can be explained by their greater contribution to model output uncertainty for variables other than GPP. For example, the parameters that control leaf development, senescence and tillering (*LAICR*, *LAILEFT*, *LAITIL* and *TBASE*) have stronger influence on LAI than directly on GPP. The *TBASE* posteriors show inconsistency between sites and years, which is consistent with the earlier BASGRA simulations for Qvidja (Heimsch et al., 2024), where temperature was found to only sporadically drive the GPP.

The progression of *ROOTDM* and *RUBISC* values show some correlation during Qvidja years, with lower *RUBISC*, thus lower photosynthetic capacity, pairing with deeper rooting depth (*ROOTDM*). This development could be interpreted as a shift towards more conservative leaf traits and larger root biomass as the grass stand ages. A similar succession is not evident for the other sites, which have a limited number of years available in the data set. To validate this hypothesis, additional multi-year site data would be required. However, the variability in *ROOTDM* values between years and sites is notably higher compared to *RUBISC*, which particularly benefited from calibration with data from multiple years or sites. The behavior of *ROOTDM* can be instead more influenced by weather conditions, such as water stress allocating more biomass to the roots. Since multi-species grass mixtures were grown at the calibration sites, the variability of *RUBISC* and *ROOTDM* between sites and years might also reflect changes in the species composition. Alternatively, the course of the values can also be affected by differences in management practices or other environmental variability. For some parameters (*LAILEFT*, *TCRES*), the year-by-year posteriors are weakly constrained, but the consistent signal results in more concentrated posteriors for the multi-year calibrations, which also show some consistency across sites. Similarly, calibration with all available data (all sites and years) shows tighter posteriors compared to other setups for some parameters (*LAICR*, *ROOTDM*, *TCRES*), which is expected with more data with a consistent signal.

The variability of harvest carbon flux between sites and harvests is underestimated by the posteriors in Fig. 8. The site-specific calibrations with all years produce narrower ranges compared to the site-year-specific calibrations, since they are informed by more data. Generally, the Qvidja measurements have lower harvest carbon flux values, which the posteriors find more easily. The difference in the range of the measurements between sites are likely caused by the differences in management. Ruukki differs from the other sites by being more intensively managed and having an organic soil with higher nitrogen availability. In contrast, the field at Qvidja received only moderate and mostly organic *N* fertilization (on average 108 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$). The training simulations did not include effects of crop *N* limitation, and the emulator might therefore not be able to fully capture differences in crop growth that stem from different *N* fertilization rates. However, for both sites some of the observations are outside the priors, including first harvests of years 2019 and 2021 in Qvidja and first harvests of years 2020 and 2021 in Ruukki. One possible explanation for the decreased performance of the first harvests could follow from the model initialization setup, with late simulation start in the beginning of May and low initial carbon pool values. The performance of harvest carbon flux estimation could benefit from confronting the model with complementary data and incorporating more constraints in calibration to better inform the prediction. We discuss this further below.

The model's predictive performance for LAI was also improved, with 10%–78% lower RMSE, when the model was constrained with GPP data (Fig. 7), due to the close relationship of the predicted variables (LAI and GPP) per implementations of the processes in BASGRA. The experiments with site-specific all-year calibration resulted in narrower

intervals for the model-estimated LAI values at Qvidja, when compared to the other sites. This is likely due to the larger amount of constraining data from Qvidja. Similar to how the GPP observations also informed the predicted LAI, calibration with only LAI data would be expected to inform the prediction of GPP. Furthermore, by combining both LAI data and GPP data in the calibration, the model performance could be further constrained. In addition, incorporating harvest carbon data to multi-objective calibration could be beneficial as some of the harvest carbon observations were outside the posteriors' range. However, the limited amount of data for harvest carbon flux likely constrains the influence on the calibration process (Cameron et al., 2022). Assimilation against LAI data could also inform the prediction of harvest carbon. In Heimsch et al. (2024) harvest yield prediction was informed with LAI data which may have enhanced the yield estimation indirectly by improving the representation of biomass growth, and with yield biomass data (Höglind et al., 2016), which expectedly improved prediction accuracy. Also, any potential structural limitations of BASGRA's harvest carbon estimation should be addressed in the model itself, and cannot be resolved through calibration.

The unbalance in temporal coverage between the different sites limits our ability to assess how the different calibration setups generalize to new sites. However, among the options tested, the multi-site calibration based on all observed years emerged as a suitable candidate for simulating unobserved sites. The multi-site calibration performed consistently across all sites (Fig. 4) and showed useful reductions in posterior uncertainty when compared to the single-site calibrations (Fig. 6). Furthermore, the multi-year calibrations also frequently outperformed single-year calibrations for harvest yields (Fig. 8), which suggests increasing spatiotemporal variability in the calibration data may improve the predictions of unobserved variables. Overall, a broader calibration set with more sites and years would be beneficial for the model performance and applicability to other sites.

Implementing a hierarchical calibration would enable simultaneously learning shared global characteristics across sites and site-specific features (Fer et al., 2021). In that case, the calibration would also benefit from calibration data with wider range of different sites and years to give a comprehensive foundation to capture hierarchical structure. The hierarchical calibration is significantly heavier computationally, as more parameters are included with different hierarchical levels, especially if the data size is increased to include multiple sites and years. In our case, the hierarchy could potentially consist of year-effect and site-effect structure to account for the detected temporal and spatial differences in posteriors. The emulator defined in this study might make the hierarchical calibration plausible due to light weight computations of the neural network and the applicability of HMC algorithm.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrated the capability of the combination of LSTM and feed-forward neural networks in learning relationships between meteorological data, plant-soil properties and carbon exchange in agroecosystems. The emulator explained over 95% of the variation of the process-based model for all predicted variables. The model successfully learned to emulate the relationships between time-series and static inputs and time-series outputs. The LSTM network efficiently learned the temporal patterns in the data and the subsequent feed-forward network decoded the LSTM output into the predicted output variables.

All of the calibration experiments performed in this study improved the emulator's performance on GPP prediction, while also informing LAI and harvest carbon estimation. Particularly, the multi-site calibration, including all available years, showed consistent performance across sites and is a potential candidate for simulating unseen sites.

The developed emulator enabled low-cost Bayesian calibration, indicating possibilities for further calibration with larger temporal or spatial scales. Future work will concentrate on addressing emulator uncertainties in calibration and using a more extensive dataset, aiming to infer a hierarchical representation of the parametric uncertainties.

The process of emulator development and calibration is generally applicable for other dynamical process-based agroecosystem models with similar characteristics, including incorporating time-series input and static input in producing a time-series output. Moving forward, applying this process to other possibly more complex agroecosystem models with other crops and management practices beyond grassland would be worth exploring.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Viivi Aakula: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Istem Fer:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Julius Vira:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Viivi Aakula, Julius Vira, and Istem Fer report financial support was provided by the Research Council of Finland, EU Horizon Europe, the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland, Business Finland, and the European Union – NextGenerationEU instrument. Viivi Aakula, Julius Vira, and Istem Fer report computational support and resources were provided by CSC – IT Center for Science, Finland. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2025.127769>.

Data availability

The data and code are publicly available in METIS data repository under the following DOI identifier: DOI [10.57707/fmi-b2share.ed61f90fe4724d3d847983944ebcd27](https://doi.org/10.57707/fmi-b2share.ed61f90fe4724d3d847983944ebcd27).

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